

Factsheet

Progress of the NBS implementation and testing in Denmark

THE CONTEXT

In Denmark, the trans4num focuses on two main NBS approaches:

- **Adjusting crop rotation:** This involves incorporating more biomass and perennial crops, such as grass and grass-clover mixtures, into existing rotations. These crops can be used for biorefinery purposes, producing protein for animals and improving nutrient balances in the soil.
- **Utilizing bio-based fertilizers:** This approach emphasizes the use of organic waste streams, such as manure, to create nutrient-rich fertilizers. This promotes nutrient circularity and minimizes nitrogen loss, benefiting both the environment and farm productivity.

Stakeholder Engagement

Interviews with key actors in the NBS value chain (biogas facilities, biorefineries, farmers and regulators) have been conducted. The information collected is guiding the future work and the planning of a major stakeholder workshop scheduled for Autumn 2024.

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Preliminary findings

Preliminary findings that assess the economic and environmental impacts of the proposed NBS interventions suggest that incorporating more grassland into crop rotations could significantly reduce nutrient leaching and improve economic outcomes for farmers.

Regulatory Sandbox

Klimafonden Skive is working at engaging four Danish ministries to establish a regulatory sandbox, a controlled environment that allows for testing new regulations and policies. This will facilitate the implementation of necessary regulatory adjustments to support large-scale NBS demonstrations.

Next steps

The Danish NBS site aims to make a significant contribution to the development and implementation of sustainable agricultural practices in Denmark by promoting collaboration, using cutting-edge research, and engaging policymakers to build a more resilient agricultural sector.